

A Comparative Study of Social Competence of Senior Secondary Students on the Basis of Religion & Gender

Shahana Siddiqui¹ & Arun Kumar²

1. Senior Research fellow, Dept. of Education, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, 226007
2. Professor, Dept. of Education, University of Lucknow, Lucknow - 226007

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Abstract

Social competence is the capacity to integrate thinking, feeling and actions to accomplish social tasks and outcomes valued in the environment and culture. Social Competence used to describe a child's effectiveness and capacity to develop and sustain long-lasting, mutually beneficial connections as well as to prevent mistreatment or victimization at the hands of others. The growth of social skills is important for figuring out how to support and shield adolescents from harmful influences and helps them realize their full potential. In this paper the researcher studied Social Competence of senior secondary students belongs to two different religion i.e. Hindu and Muslim religion. The data of the research was collected through lottery method of simple random sampling technique. The sample of the study consist 600 senior secondary students. The researcher used Social Competence tool to collect data from the sample. It is developed by the researcher. The findings of the research revealed a significant difference between social competence of male and female students. Female students of Hindu and Muslim religion outperforms their counterparts.

Keywords: Social Competence, Senior Secondary Students, Religion and Gender.

Introduction

The [socially] competent individual is one who is able to make use of environmental and personal resources to achieve good development outcome (Waters & Sroufe, 1983 p. 81).

Social competence means to take another's perspective concerning a condition and to learn from previous experience and apply that learning and knowledge to the ever-changing social aspect. The ability to respond flexibly and properly defines a person's ability to control & handle the social challenges that are before us all. Social competence is the base upon which expectations for future interactions with others are constructed and upon which children develop a perception of their own conduct and actions. Social experiences are intimately associated with emotional competence. It is unlikely that social competence exists without appropriate emotional functioning also present.

Waters & Sroufe (1983) believed that it is essential to be socially competent; the characteristics of socially competent persons are problem solving behaviour, perspective taking and person perception. The competent individual is one who is able to make use of environmental and personal resources to achieve a good developmental outcome.

Rotheram (1987) defined social competence as academic competence and positive relationships with peers and teachers. He claimed that competence with teachers likely requires different skills from competence with peers or in academics.

Cavell (1990) proposed a three-time model i.e., social performance, social adjustment & social skill. The first and most advanced level is called a social adjustment. Social adjustment is that condition where the child is developmentally on focus for achieving appropriate social goals. This level considers how well the adolescents meet the expectations of parents, teachers, friends, and society. Most of the children achieve this extent without problems but when difficulties begin the

child often looks 'different' and may be socially rejected, detached or isolated from his/her peers. Social performance is the second level which means how well the student performs in social situations and what circumstances may create problems for the student. Social skills regarded as the last basic level which means the specific abilities the child avails within a social situation. This level incorporates how the child responds to the conditions as well as how the situation is encoded.

In this study the researcher used the three tier model of social competence given by **Cavell (1990)** to develop the research tool on social competence to collect data.

Spitzberg (2003) Social competence is the term that frequently encompasses additional constructs such as interpersonal communication, social communication, and social skills. Social communication assumes that the goal can be fulfilled through interaction with another person using language & non-verbal communication. These skills are also assumed to be goal oriented. Social skills suppose that these are behaviours that are repeated and goal-oriented.

Annamalai (2011) stated that social competency of male students is more than female students and social competency had a significant relationship with social intelligence, social adjustment and social skill.

Senior Secondary Students: In the present study senior secondary students are those who have passed the Xth standard examination from a recognized board and would like to continue their education towards a senior secondary certification, equivalent to XII.

Religion: Religion is a particular core system of beliefs and practice that are generally accepted by many people's or sects. For the present study only two religion are taken i.e. Hindu religion and Muslim religion.

Gender: Girls, boys, males, females and persons who identify as having a different gender all exhibit roles, behaviours, expressions, and identities that are socially produced. It affects how individuals behave and interact, how they view themselves and others, and how power and resources are distributed in society. For the present study only males and females are taken into the sample.

Objectives of the study:

1. To compare Social Competence of male and female students.
2. To compare Social Competence of male and female Hindu students.
3. To compare Social Competence of male and female Muslim students.

Hypotheses of the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the Social Competence of male and female students.
2. There is no significant difference in the Social Competence of male and female Hindu students.
3. There is no significant difference in the Social Competence of male and female Muslim Students.

Delimitations of the study:

1. The study is confined to Lucknow city only.
2. In this study only male and female students of senior secondary schools are taken for the sample.
3. Only U. P. board, I.S.C board and I.C.S.E board students are included in the study.

Methodology & Sample of the study:

The Descriptive survey method is used for the sample of the study. In this study the population consists of a group of class XI students including all boards (U.P, I.S.C, I.C.S.E. boards) who are between the ages of 15 and 19. The data collection technique apply in the study is simple random sampling technique.

The research is carried out on 600 students of senior secondary schools students with equal number of boys and girls (300 boys and 300 girls) from eleven different colleges with equal proportion of both the religion (150 male Hindu, 150 female Hindu, and 150 male Muslim 150 female Muslim). In this study the responses on Social Competence are assessed through Social Competence Scale (SCS) developed by the researcher. The statistics techniques used in the study are Mean, S.D, C.R. (Critical Ratio) and "r" (coefficient of correlation) to get the results.

Analysis of Data:

Analysis 1:

According to Ho. 1, there is no significant difference in the social competence of male and female students. Ho.1 is interpreted by the critical ratio (C.R.).

To study Ho.1, the researcher calculated the mean scores and standard deviation of social competence of 300 male and 300 female students (total 600) of senior secondary school and then calculated the C.R. value between the two groups (male and female). An analysis is given in Table.1.

Table. 1 - Mean, S.D. & C.R. of Social Competence of male and female students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	C.R.	p-value	Result
Social Competence of Male students	300	172.47	17.79	5.412	.00	Significant
Social Competence of Female students	300	179.76	15.112			

Level of significance at 0.05=1.96

.05>P

Analysis of Result:

Table number 1 indicates that the mean scores of social competence of male students is 172.47 with S.D. 17.79. The mean scores of social competence of female students is 179.76 with S.D. 15.112. The calculated C.R. value is 5.412, with the degree of freedom 598, and the p value is .00.

Figure. 1 - A Bar diagram displaying the difference between Social competence of Male & Female students

Interpretation of the Result:

The results and bar diagram no. 1 stated that the female students were found to have significantly higher social competence as compared to the male students. When we observe the difference between the mean values of the two groups, it appears to be only 5.412, showing that the C.R. is greater than the table value. P value is also less than table value, which shows that the difference is significant and considerable at the 0.05 level between the social competence of male and female students of senior secondary schools.

So, the null hypothesis (Ho. 1) is rejected, and it can be said that there is a significant difference in the social competence of male and female students. Thus, a generalization can be made that the

female students of senior secondary schools show a higher level of social competence than the male students of senior secondary schools.

Discussion of the Result:

The findings of Ho. 1 show that the female students of senior secondary schools show a higher level of social competence than the male students of senior secondary schools, and there is a significant difference between the social competence of male and female students. Female students are more socially competent than the male students. It may be because of their pro-social behavior, and social adjustment characteristics as they are able to handle social settings, which indicates their better social skills, improves their social performance, and can adjust easily to the environment. This indicates that female students are better at social competence. **Amandeep (2016) and Bhaliya (2015)** study findings revealed that there was a significant difference between the social competence of male and female students, and female students have a significantly higher level of social competence as compared to their counterparts.

Analysis 2:

According to Ho.2, there is no significant difference in the social competence of male and female Hindu students. Ho.2 is interpreted by the critical ratio (C.R.).

To study Ho.2, the researcher calculated the mean scores and standard deviation of social competence of 150 male and 150 female Hindu senior secondary students (total 300) and then calculated the C.R. value between the two groups (male and female). An analysis is given in Table. 2.

Table. 2 - Mean, S.D. & C.R. of Social Competence of Male and Female Hindu students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	C.R.	p-value	Result
Social Competence of Male Hindu students	150	171.45	17.016	4.500	.000	Significant
Social Competence of Female Hindu students	150	180.10	16.280			

Level of significance at 0.05=1.97

.05>P

Analysis of Result:

Table number 2 indicates that the mean scores of social competence of male Hindu students is 171.45 with S.D. 17.016. The mean scores of social competence of female Hindu students is 180.10 with S.D. 16.280. The calculated C.R. value is 4.500, with degree of freedom 298, and the p value is .000.

Figure. 2 - A Bar diagram displaying the difference between Social competence of Male & Female Hindu students

Interpretation of the Result:

The results and bar diagram no. 2 stated that the female Hindu students were found to have significantly higher social competence as compared to their male counterparts. When we observe the difference between the mean values of the two groups, it appears to be 4.500, showing that the C.R. value is greater than the table value. P value is also less than 0.05, which shows that the difference is significant and considerable at the 0.05 level between the social competence of male and female Hindu senior secondary students.

So, the null hypothesis (Ho. 2) is rejected, and it can be said that there is a significant difference in the social competence of male and female Hindu students. Thus, a generalization can be made that the female Hindu students show a higher level of social competence than their male counterparts.

Discussion of the Result:

The findings of Ho. 2 show that the mean score of social competence of female students is higher than that of male students of Hindu religion. There is a significant difference between the groups, which showed that Hindu female students are more competent than their male counterparts. The students' social competence is significantly influenced by gender. In this instance, females are more socially competent than males, which means that females may have better mental health, have more opportunities to express themselves, and may have supportive families who enable them to advance in various areas. Parents, instructors, and friends offered greater assistance to females in helping them deal with issues and perform well in social situations.

Analysis 3:

According to Ho.3, there is no significant difference in the social competence of male and female Muslim students. Ho.3 is interpreted by the critical ratio (C.R.).

To study Ho.3, the researcher calculated the mean scores and standard deviation of social competency of 150 male and 150 female Muslim senior secondary students (total 300) and then calculated t-value between the two groups (male and female). An analysis is given in Table. 3.

Table. 3 - Mean, S.D. & C.R. of Social Competence of Male and Female Muslim students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	C.R.	p-value	Result
Social Competence of Male Muslim students	150	173.49	18.533	3.137	.002	Significant
Social Competence of Female Muslim students	150	179.42	13.893			

Level of significance at 0.05=1.97

.05>P

Analysis of Result:

Table number 3 indicates that the mean scores of social competence of male Muslim students is 173.49 with S.D. 18.533. The mean scores of social competence of female Muslim students is 179.42 with S.D. 13.893. The calculated C.R. value is 3.137, with degree of freedom 298, and the p value is .002.

Figure. 3 -
A Bar diagram displaying the difference between Social competence of Male & Female Muslim students

Interpretation of the Result:

The results and bar diagram no. 3 stated that female students were found to have significantly higher social competence as compared to male students of Muslim religion. When we observe the difference between the mean values of the two groups, it appears to be 3.137, showing that the C.R. value is greater than the table value. P value is also less than 0.05, which shows that the difference is significant and considerable at the 0.05 level of significance between the social competence of male and female Muslim senior secondary students.

So, the null hypothesis (Ho. 3) is rejected, and it can be said that there is a significant difference in the social competence of male and female Muslim students. Thus, a generalization can be made that the female Muslim senior secondary students show a higher level of social competence than their male counterparts.

Discussions of the Result:

The findings of Ho. 3 show that the mean score of social competence of female students is higher than that of male students of the Muslim religion. There is a significant difference between the groups, which showed that the Muslim female students are more competent than their male counterparts. The students' social competence is significantly influenced by gender. In this instance, females are more socially competent than males, which means that females may have better mental health, have more opportunities to express themselves, and may have supportive families who enable them to advance in various areas. Parents, instructors, and friends offered greater assistance to females in helping them deal with issues and perform well in social situations. **Singh. (2013)** also supported the findings of the study and the results revealed that the male and female Muslim students have a significant difference in respect of social competence and female students are more competent than male students.

Conclusions: Social competence is a complex process which begins in childhood and lasts into puberty and beyond. The present study was focused to analyze the social competence of senior secondary students with respect to their gender and religion. It comes to the conclusion that there is significant difference in the social competence of male and female students and female students demonstrate a higher level of social competence than male pupils. Also, it has been discovered that Hindu female students exhibit higher levels of social competence than Hindu male students. The result also revealed that Muslim female students in senior secondary schools exhibit higher levels of social competence than Muslim male pupils.

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